

**THE ROLE OF THE FAMILY IN PREVENTING YOUNG PEOPLE
FROM THE DISEASE OF SHOPOGOLISM**

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Abstract: *this article analyzes the role of the family in protecting young people from the disease of shopaholicism. The article reveals the purposeful direction of demand for ration and non-rational consumer products and the fulfillment of consumer desires in them without violating the requirements of moral norms.*

Key words: *youth, shopaholicism, depression, consumer culture, spiritual education, family, society.*

Introduction. Shopaholicism, in turn, is a certain disease that occurs in young people and adults as a result of an increased desire to buy unnecessary goods.

“Patients” with this disease are always in a rush to buy things. They also spend their money on unnecessary expenses and face many financial problems as a result. These non-rational consumption needs can harm the physical and financial condition of young people and cause them to move away from their clearly defined goals.

Nonrational consumption threatens the physical and mental development of young people. Consumerism encourages people to find the meaning and value of life through consumption, and consumption has become the main way of satisfying people's psyche and self-realization. The value of people is confirmed by the value

of things, and the value of things confirms and shows the value of people. “In today’s society, the institutionalization of consumption is taking place, that is, consumption is becoming not only an individual process or function, but also an ideological structure aimed at satisfying human consumption needs. Postmodern society turns the productive, creative person into a consumer person. At the same time, the ideology of consumption is voluntary-compulsory. On the one hand, the consumer is declared to be free in his choice, but on the other hand, consumption is declared to some extent to be a measure of social merit: the person who consumes more has a greater social status. Will have The nature of consumption has changed. It was transformed from a material practice into a socio-cultural practice, and transformed social relations into consumer relations [1].

It is unfortunate that many of our young people consider buying goods from many markets, supermarkets and online stores as the main meaning of their life. Many mental illnesses and social problems are increasing due to consumption activities based on extravagance. For example, although the children of some wealthy families live by consuming a lot, “depression” and “boring” have become a mantra. Depression and death from overwork plague the townspeople even more. In a sense, it can be said that these issues are inextricably linked with the spread of consumerism [2]. The famous English economist Schumacher said, “The unlimited needs of people can be realized only in the spiritual sphere, and it cannot be achieved in the material sphere” [3] stated that. In fact, consumer culture is a concept that encourages people to provide a place to live well, to satisfy their material and spiritual needs. But it is a fact that young people are exchanging consumer culture for unnatural consumer culture. In the end, it can only cause them to become slaves to products and become tired of striving for future goals, thereby negatively affecting their healthy and well-rounded development.

Another deep-rooted source of overconsumption is the irrational perception of human greed. For this reason, “Determining practical measures for the implementation of specific tasks regarding the mechanisms of the application of

the methods aimed at the formation of the consumer culture of the population and the continuous improvement of the needs of the population, and as a result of which people are harmful to natural resources to a certain extent increasing the influence, in turn, the need to constantly expand the knowledge of the population about consumer culture remains an objective necessity” [4].

In order to prevent these situations, first of all, parents should not be indifferent to the future of the family and children, they should try to find a solution from the time when the husband or wife first notices the beginning of these situations. At the same time, as they say, “birds do what they see in their nests”, parents themselves unknowingly lead their children to this quagmire. First of all, it is necessary to target family purchases and avoid excessive spending. Family purchases are mainly influenced by various factors. The first factor is the behavior of the family. From a purchasing point of view, the behavior of a family can only be evaluated after studying the behavior of all members of that family. After all, the family is a group of people, and the decision of each member affects the decision of the whole group. When considering family purchases, it is necessary to consider that its members buy mainly in two directions: for personal use and for the well-being of the whole group.

When studying the family as a consumer group, special attention should be paid to sociological indicators. They are: unity, flexibility and communication. Family unity is an emotional connection between family members. The specified characteristic shows the level of reliability and closeness of family members to each other, describes the feeling of unity or separation of family members from each other. Flexibility is the ability of the family to change the tasks of its members, change the roles and the level of influence during the purchase. Changes in the list occur at different stages of family existence. Communication is the positive and negative emotions that arise and exist within the specified kinship system. Positive feelings of family members towards each other allow them to share their needs and preferences with each other, which helps to develop and

establish positive relationships and increases the level of family communication. Positive emotional habits of family members can be related to the following: putting yourself in his place, the ability to listen, support the person close to him, the desire and efforts to understand. Negative communication habits have a negative impact on mutual understanding and mutual support between family members. It significantly reduces the level of communication in the family as a whole. Negative emotional habits of family members include: hypocrisy, excessive and unreasonable criticism of behavior, hiding one's opinion.

Conclusions and recommendations

In today's era of globalization, comprehensive systematization of young people and their consumer desires is more necessary than ever. Because the lack of curbing of various economic, political, and religious needs will ultimately distance young people from spiritual and moral perfection. The main solution to such issues starts with the family first. It is a fact that the wise spending of family income by adults has an impact on the education of young people.

In order to prevent a disease such as shopaholicism, it is very important for young people to be patient and control their ego. In order to correct this situation, family support is also necessary for him to constantly communicate with people, work on himself and manage his financial situation independently.

We put forward the following recommendations to prevent shopaholicism:

1. **Financial Planning:** It is very important to analyze your financial situation and start financial planning. You need to create a financial plan every month, avoid unnecessary expenses and make it possible to spend money effectively.

2. **Set your thoughts:** When you feel the urge to buy unnecessary things, it's important to set your thoughts and figure out what steps to take to reduce that anxiety.

3. **Get support:** If you're struggling with shopaholics, ask friends or family members for help. When you can ask for their support, you will have more power to fight shopaholicism.

4. Get help from a psychologist: If shopaholicism is limiting your life, seek help from a psychologist. They can give you the advice you need and help you deal with shopaholics.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Коблева Э.А., Схаляхо З.Ч. Идеология потребления в духовной жизни современного общества // Исторические, философские, политические и юридические науки, культурология и искусствоведение. Тамбов: Грамота, 2017.С. 115-118.
2. Гуров О.Н. Границы «человеческого» и «технического» : на примере творчества Д. Кроненберга : дисс ... канд. филос. наук. – М.: 2022. - 191 с.
3. Шумахер Э.Ф. Малое прекрасно. Экономика, в которой люди имеют значение [Текст] / Эрнст Шумахер ; пер. с англ. Д. Аронсона. – М.: Изд. дом Высш. шк. экономики, 2012. - 351 с.
4. Xaydarov A.N. O‘zbekistonda aholi iste’mol madaniyatini takomillashtirishning ijtimoiy-falsafiy masalalari. Fals. fan. bo‘y. fals. dok. (PhD) diss. avtoref. – Samarqand, 2021. –B.20.

